

Insect resistance

Tainung 68, the first BPH-resistant Japonica cultivar developed in Taiwan

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Japonica cultivars, which occupy more than 90% of the planted area in Taiwan, are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH). Efforts to transfer BPH resistance from indica to japonica rices have resulted in the release of BPH-resistant selection Chianung 250, the first BPH-resistant japonica cultivar developed in Taiwan. The Subcommittee on Varietal Registration of the Taiwan Rice Improvement Council unanimously recommended its release 1 June 1982.

The new cultivar, officially named Tainung 68, was selected in 1976 from the cross Nankai-yu 114//Nankai-yu 77//Tainan 5²/ASD 7, made in 1973 at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station. The resistance to BPH inherited from

Correlations between silvershoots and panicle and tiller numbers

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Gall midge infestation is thought to stimulate profuse tillering. Therefore the association among silvershoots and tiller and panicle numbers was assessed. Data on the three attributes were taken on variety Sita on 27 randomly selected hills from each of 11 plots, 10 treated with insecticides and 1 untreated. Data were collected after the emergence of panicles, about 1 month after insecticides were applied.

Total correlation coefficients between silvershoots and tillers, silvershoots and panicles, and tillers and panicles and partial correlation between silvershoots and panicles were determined. Estimates of total and partial correlation coefficients for the 11 treatments were pooled

Table 1. Resistance^a to disease and insect pest of Tainung 68 in Taiwan, China.

Cultivar	Blast	Neck blast	Bacterial blight	Brown planthopper ^b	
				15 DS	45 DS
Tainung 68	MR-S	MR-S	MR-S	S	R
Tainung 67 (check)	S-HS	S-HS	MS	S	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bDS = days after seeding.

Table 2. Agronomic performance of Tainung 68 in Taiwan, China (av of 1979-81).

Cultivar	Maturity (days)		Height (cm)		Yield ^a (t/ha)	
	1st crop	2d crop	1st crop	2d crop	1st crop	2d crop
Tainung 68	115	97	94	99	6.3	4.6
Tainung 67 (check)	116	98	96	103	6.8	4.6

^aRecorded at Pintung, southern Taiwan.

ASD7 is expressed at late growing stages. Tainung 68 also has some resistance to blast and bacterial leaf blight diseases (Table 1). Most agronomic characters are desirable, with good yields in the second crop, particularly in the southern part of the island (Table 2).

Currently grown cultivar Tainung 67 is susceptible to BPH, which occurs severely in southern Taiwan during the hot, wet second crop season. Tainung 68, is a promising alternative and an important source of BPH resistance in breeding programs. ■

using a multiple covariance model.

Tillering correlated positively with silvershoots (see table). Estimates of correlation coefficients varied from 0.1326 to 0.8402, significant in 9 cases. The pooled correlation coefficient was 0.4718, significant at the 0.01 level.

Tillers correlated positively with pani-

cles. Estimates of coefficients varied from 0.1731 to 0.6898, significant in 9 cases. Estimate of the pooled correlation coefficient (0.5518) was significant at the 0.01 level.

Of 11 estimates of the correlation coefficient between silvershoots and panicles, only one was significant. This sug-

Estimates of total and partial correlation coefficients^a between silvershoots, tillers, and panicle numbers at Bihar, India.

Treatment	r ₁₂	r ₂₃	r ₁₃	r _{13·2}
Foratox	0.8402**	0.6056**	0.0880 ^{ns}	0.9751**
BPMC	0.1326 ^{ns}	0.5227**	0.0096 ^{ns}	0.0936 ^{ns}
Ekalux	0.4002*	0.6898**	0.1438 ^{ns}	0.3536*
Carbofuran	0.5604**	0.3551 ^{ns}	0.2573 ^{ns}	0.5608**
Carbaryl	0.7960**	0.1731 ^{ns}	0.0828 ^{ns}	0.6428**
Lindane	0.4099*	0.5548**	0.2604 ^{ns}	0.6428**
Diazinon	0.6723**	0.5035**	0.4743*	0.2125 ^{ns}
Tamaron	0.3408 ^{ns}	0.6370**	0.2242 ^{ns}	0.6089**
CFVP	0.5467**	0.5563**	0.2653 ^{ns}	0.2444 ^{ns}
Monocil	0.5467**	0.5563**	0.2095 ^{ns}	0.7381**
Control	0.5581**	0.4650*	0.0937 ^{ns}	0.2257 ^{ns}
Pooled	0.4718**	0.5518**	0.0029	0.3156*

^a1 = silvershoots, 2 = tillers, 3 = panicles. * = significant at 5% level. ** = significant at 1% level. ns = not significant.

gests no association between the two characters. The pooled estimate was also nonsignificant.

The absence of correlation between silvershoots and panicles and the significant correlation between silvershoots and tillering support the popular belief that silvershoots increase tillering, compensating for panicle loss. But it also may be argued that a hill containing a greater number of tillers is more susceptible to gall midge attack, because it provides more points. As such, more

tillers would be the cause of silvershoots.

Estimates of partial correlation coefficients between silvershoots and panicles after eliminating the effect of tiller differences were made. All estimates except one were negative, varying from -0.9751 to -0.0936 and significant in 5 cases. The only positive estimate was also small and nonsignificant. The pooled estimate of the partial correlation coefficient was -0.3156 , significant at the 0.05 level.

A partial regression analysis using the covariance model $y = f(\text{Tr.}; X_1 X_2 X_3)$

where y stands for panicle, X_1 for silvershoot, and X_2 for tiller estimated the loss due to silvershoots for the pooled data. The result was $y = 1.84 - 0.3975 X_1 + 0.4584 X_2$. The estimate of R , the multiple correlation coefficient, was 0.7791, significant at the 0.01 level. Both partial regression coefficients were also significant at 0.01. The partial regression equation suggests that the expected net effect of a unit increase in the number of silvershoots is a drop of 0.4 in the number of panicles. ■

Resistance of modern rice varieties to the brown planthopper in Thailand

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Outbreaks of the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* have caused a rapid spread of ragged stunt disease in the central Thailand plain since 1973. But RD9, the first BPH-resistant variety released in 1975, has not been widely accepted because of its susceptibility to many diseases and its poor grain quality.

A greenhouse experiment was designed to determine the resistance mechanism in three varieties released in 1981 — RD21 (DML 105/Nang-Mol S-4/IR26), RD23 (RD7/IR32/RD1), and RD25 (DML 105/IR2061-214-2-3-3 // DML 105/IR26) — and in an RD7 mutant developed by gamma-irradiation which had shown BPH resistance. Experimental procedures were those used in the International Brown Planthopper Biotype Collaborative Project.

A free-choice feeding experiment showed no significant difference in the number of insects feeding on resistant and susceptible varieties. Antibiosis was indicated: BPH survival after 12 days was 6% on RD21, 7.5% on RD7 mutant, 14% on RD9, 20% on RD23, 20% on RD25, and 36% on RD1 (Fig. 1). The population buildup study also confirmed antibiosis reaction in RD21, RD23, RD25, and RD7 mutant. RD25

1. Survival of brown planthopper on modern rice varieties in Thailand.

2. Population buildup of brown planthopper (BPH) on different rice varieties 4 weeks after release of 3 pairs of adults, Thailand.

showed the highest resistance (no population increase) to BPH; RD1 produced 247 insects 4 weeks after release of 3 mated BPH pairs (Fig. 2).

Reaction of selected rice varieties to whorl maggot *Hydrellia* spp.

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During 1981 kharif, 22 varieties were grown in 20-hill rows. Two plantings were done, one at the usual time and the second 15 days later. Recommended management practices were followed.

The number of whorl maggot-damaged leaves was recorded on 10 hills/variety at 30 and 45 days after transplanting (see table). Ptb 12 and Ptb 21 had the least damage, Ptb 19 the most damage. ■

Incidence of whorl maggot damage on rice varieties at Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Whorl maggot incidence (%)
ARC6632	10.1
Banglei	8.5
Chemban	9.3
Chempan	11.6
Chitteri	10.7
Cheriya Chitteri	11.4
Kula Peruvela	11.4
L x H/2-281	12.4
Leaung 152	11.7
Nagrasal	12.9
Ptb 12	3.4
Ptb 19	16.5
Ptb 21	5.5
Ptb 33	13.0
Parakulam	10.5
Sulai	12.9
T 10	8.8
Vellai Langayan	11.4
Valsara Champara	14.3
Vellathil cheera	11.7
Lal Basumati	10.3
TN1 (susceptible check)	11.1